

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

GUIDED WAVE NDE AND RESIDUAL STRENGTH OF COMPOSITE PANELS WITH STIFFENER IMPACT DAMAGE

Andrew Ellison, Hyungsuk Eric Kim, Hyonny Kim
University of California San Diego, USA

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Introduction/Motivation

- Low velocity blunt impact potentially generates internal damage to composite structure that has low/no external visibility
- Presence of blunt impact damage modes on primary stiffened structure may cause significant reduction or residual strength
- **Objective:** Identify and characterize the blunt impact damage modes and estimate residual strength reduction through NDE measurements

GSE Impact/Contact

Overall Experimental Summary

- Stringer panel compression after impact
- Relate NDE quantities to residual strength:
 - Two major specimen types:
 - I. Cap impacted stringer strength/cripling specimens
 - II. Flange impacted stringer post-buckling response specimens
 - Non-destructive evaluation techniques
 - Ultrasonic pulse-echo; 5 MHz
 - X-ray computed tomography (CT)
 - Ultrasonic guided wave line scanning (novel)

As manufactured 5-stringer panel

Panel Material: unidirectional
Toray T800-3900-2
carbon/epoxy

Layup – both skin & stringer
16 plies quasi-isotropic
[45/-45/0/45/90/-45/0/90]_s

Impact Testing

- Low velocity 25.4 mm radius metal tip pendulum impact with clamped-type boundary conditions
 - Stringer impact at mid-span center of cap
 - 12 impacts performed at nominal energy levels: 28, 47, and 66 J
 - Impacts generally produced damage within the top of the stringer cap with higher impact energies creating damage within the stringer web

- Skin-side mid-flange impact
 - Impacts were performed at nominally 65 and 84 J
 - Impacts damage:
 - Trapezoidal-shaped skin-flange disbond areas with shorter side towards the stringer interior
 - Delamination within skin and stringer flange

Cap impact setup

Flange impact setup

Nondestructive Evaluation (UT, CT, UGW)

Three main NDE techniques were employed:

- Ultrasonic Pulse-Echo Scanning (UT), handheld A-scan and automated C-scan
 - Rapid characterization of detected damage, but slow to apply to large areas
 - Unable to detect damage underneath other damage features
- X-ray Computed Tomography (CT)
 - High fidelity 3D dataset of internal damage
 - Difficult to deploy in service and limited scanning area
- Ultrasonic Guided Wave Line Scanning (UGW)
 - Rapid deployment
 - Can detect internal structural damage such as in stiffening elements
 - Does not give image of damage shape

Cap Impact NDE

- Good CT characterization
- Poor UT characterization due to stringer curvature
- Primary features of interest
 - Delaminated zones
 - Zones with fiber breakage
 - Damage interaction with stringer radius

Damage area estimated by handheld pulse-echo UT for the three impact energy levels

UT C-scan TOF map

Fiber damage at stringer radius

66J cap impact CT slice showing damage traveling down the cap web.

47J cap impact CT slice

Flange Impact NDE

- Good UT characterization
- Lower quality CT characterization due to larger specimen size
- Primary features of interest
 - Disbond between stringer and skin
 - Damage within the skin and stringer flange laminates

S4F2 (65J impact)

S3F2 (84J impact)

Damage area estimated by handheld UT A-scan

CT Dataset Slice

Ultrasonic Pulse-echo Time of Flight Map

TOF Map Color Coded by Damaged Region

Ultrasonic Guided Wave Test

- Path from Excitation to Receiver is waveguide
- Ultrasonic Guided Waves (UGW) transmitted across the stringer to investigate the skin+stiffener panel
 - Scanned along the stringer at multiple regions of stringers for both flange and cap at various impact levels
- Hybrid semi-contact point scan
 - Excitation by Mini-Impactor
 - High intensity broadband frequency excitation generated
 - frequency content up to ~200 kHz on composite
 - Excellent Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) for air-coupled transducer
 - Receivers are Broadband Air-coupled Transducers (BAT)
 - located before (Rec1) and after (Rec2) stringer along UGW path
- UGW testing performed from exterior skin side

UGW Test

- Mini-Impactor generates broadband excitation that transmits as waves through composite structure
- Gating of signal needed to isolate early-arrival wave info
 - Hann window gated for wave packets that contains significant information about impact damage
 - 1st wave packet for time feature
 - 1st + 2nd wave packet for amplitude feature
- Mini-Impactor generates consistent excitation
 - Plot shows 10 repeated Mini-Impactor tests
- Automated system under development for robust data acquisition and reduced operator error

UGW Features – Flange Impact Damage

- **Time feature**, Time-of-Flight (TOF), of 1st wave packet extracted and plotted per scan # (i.e., position) along the stringer
- Time delay not observed from pre-impact baseline time feature plot
- Significant time delay at impact region measured from post-impact scans

UGW Features – Flange Impact Damage

- T_{COI} = Time index at impact center (scan #11)
 - T_{avg} = Average time index from baseline
- } Significant difference correlates to damaged area

Region	Impact (J)	TOA @ COI (μs)	$T_{COI} - T_{AVG}$ (μs)
S3F1	84.48	113.3	5.0
S3F2	82.72	114.3	4.6
S4F1	64.81	112.2	3.5
S4F2	64.81	112.1	2.8

UGW Features – Flange Damage

- UT C-scan result from flange impact mapped into three damage modes: **skin laminate damage**, **skin-stringer disbond**, and **flange laminate damage**
 - Time delay compared to the **skin laminate damage** modes from UT C-scan (pixel count along path) → strong correlation found
 - UT scan shows no (less) skin laminate damage mode at impact center; time delay drops for UGW as well

S3F1 84J UT C-Scan Tri-Color

UGW Features – Flange Damage

- **Amplitude feature:** Root-Mean-Square (RMS) of 1st and 2nd wave packets extracted and plotted per scan # (position) along panel
- RMS value reduces with presence of damage (reduced raw signal amplitude)

UGW Features – Flange Damage

- **Skin-stringer disbond** damage mode from UT C-scan (pixel count along path) compared to the UGW amplitude feature
 - UGW provides rough estimation of disbond span – verified via comparison to UT results
 - RMS magnitude higher at impact center – due to no skin laminate damage under impactor

S3F1 84J UT C-Scan Tri-Color

S4F2 65J UT C-Scan Tri-Color

— UGW RMS Magnitude
— UT Disbond Pixel Count

— UGW RMS Magnitude
— UT Disbond Pixel Count

S3F1 84J Damage Features Comparison

S4F2 65J Damage Features Comparison

Region	Impact (J)	RMS @ COI (mV)
S3F1	84.48	3.68
S3F2	82.72	3.79
S4F1	64.81	4.42
S4F2	64.81	4.42

UGW Features – Cap Damage

For the cap impact panel

- no damage on the skin region
- time feature results does not identify damage from 1st wave packet (no time delay)

--- 1st Packet Hann Gate
- - - 1st + 2nd Packet Hann Gate

UGW Features – Cap Damage

- RMS amplitude feature of first two wave packets extracted and plotted per scan # along the stringer
 - RMS peak increases with more severe damage present on stringer cap
 - due to less energy leakage thru stringer cap path
- X-ray CT-scan at impact center location shows:
 - Cap crown damage stayed similar for 47J and 67J impact
 - Damage progressed down to the stringer web for higher impact level

Region	Impact (J)	RMS Peak (mV)
S3C1	28.36	4.173
S3C2	47.68	4.403
S3C3	65.72	5.331

Residual Strength Testing – Cap

- Cap-impacted specimens were tested for residual compression strength
 - Skin trimmed to within 7 mm from the stringer flange to inhibit unsupported skin buckling
 - Primary failure mode is stringer crippling

Results summary for Cap Impacted Specimens

Test ID	Spec. Type	Impact Energy [J]	Peak Imp. Force [kN]	Damage Area [mm ²]	Peak Comp. Load [kN]																	
S2C2	Cap	47.6	10.7	1050	205																	
S4C3	Cap	47.1	10.6	1070	202																	
SSC3	Cap	66.5	1070	204	S4C2	Cap	66.7	11.4	1140	210	S4PC1	Cap	--	--	--	460	S1PC2	Cap	--	--	--	478
S4C2	Cap	66.7	11.4	1140	210																	
S4PC1	Cap	--	--	--	460																	
S1PC2	Cap	--	--	--	478																	

SSC3, 66.5 J

Residual Strength Testing – Flange

- Flange-impacted specimens were tested for residual compression strength
 - Skin left untrimmed to promote skin buckling/post-buckling
 - Primary failure modes include:
 - Initial buckling of skin
 - Disbond growth - unzipping
 - Failure of the skin/flange laminate due to impact damage

Results Summary for Flange Impacted Specimens

Test ID	Spec. Type	Impact Energy [J]	Peak Imp. Force [kN]	Damage Area [mm ²]	Peak Comp. Load [kN]
S4F2	Flange	64.8	14.4	2140	376
S3F1	Flange	84.5	16.1	2540	347
S3F2	Flange	82.7	15.9	2650	347
S5PF1	Flange	--	--	--	471

UGW Residual Strength Estimation - Flange

- UGW measurements identify presence of damage
 - Preliminarily: can correlate to damage location, mode, and impact level for the stiffened panel
 - Could be used for residual strength estimation
- Amplitude feature for the flange damage scan comparison shows wave energy decrease (wave scattering) at the center of impact with increased impact level
- Time of arrival comparison shows increased delay in TOF at the center of impact with increased impact damage
- Narrowband frequency testing should increase probability of estimation

Mini-BAT

Conclusions

- Impact damage for both cap and flange are identified from semi-contact UGW
 - Scanning performed only from external skin-side of stiffened panel
 - Time of flight of UGW found to be sensitive to damage modes present in the skin
 - Amplitude feature of UGW allows differentiation of damage location, showing
 - energy absorption for skin/flange damage
 - energy increase for cap damage (no skin damage)
- Features of the UGW results shows sensitivity to impact energy level for flange damage
 - could be used to estimate residual strength of the stiffened structure
 - results may be frequency dependent

Acknowledgements: this work was supported by the NASA Advanced Composites Project No. 15-ACP1-0021 and FAA Joint Advance Materials and Structures Center of Excellence (JAMS CoE).